

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

АГРОБИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА СИЛОСНЫХ КУЛЬТУР В УСЛОВИЯХ ГОРНОЙ ЗОНЫ АРМЕНИИ

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AGROBIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF SILAGE CROPS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE MOUNTAINOUS ZONE OF ARMENIA

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Аннотация

В деле создания прочной кормовой базы в республике и увеличения производства силосных культур первостепенное значение имеет расширение посевных площадей кормовых однолетних культур.

Почвенно - климатические условия высокогорья Лорийского марза Армении, а также богатый типичный альпийский растительный покров дают возможность для развития животноводства.

В условиях сел Леджан и Пушкино Степанаванского региона проводились отдельный и совместный посевы сорго, подсолнухи и вики.

Исследования показали, что в обоих местностях совместный посев подсолнухи и вики обеспечивает получению высокого и качественного урожая.

Abstract

Expanding the area under annual fodder crops and increasing the production of silage crops is of paramount importance in creating a solid forage base in the republic.

The soil and climatic conditions of the highlands in Lori region of Armenia, as well as the rich typical alpine vegetation cover provide an opportunity for the development of animal husbandry.

In conditions of Lejan and Pushkino villages of the Stepanavan province separate and joint sowings of sorghum, sunflowers and vetch were carried out.

Studies have shown that in both areas, the combined sowing of sunflowers and vetch provides rich and high-quality yield.

Ключевые слова: сорго, подсолнуха, вика, совместный посев, урожай.

Keywords: sorghum, sunflower, vetch, joint sowing, yield.

Introduction

The highlands of Lori region of the Republic are distinguished by a species variety and rich alpine pasture. The total territory of the highlands occupies 119.3 hectares, out of which 60.6 hectares are suitable for agricultural lands, among which 19.8 are pastures.

Temperate climatic conditions, rich vegetation cover of pastures create favorable conditions for the development of animal husbandry.

One of the main conditions for manufacturing livestock products is the creation of a solid forage base. If during the grazing period the animals are provided with a sufficient amount of succulent high-quality feed, then this cannot be observed for the stall barn housing period. During this period, hay and low-quality concentrated feed serve as animal feed [Aghababyan Sh.M. 1970, Dolukhanyan, L.G. 2001, Beluchenko I.S., Melnik O.A.2010].

Considering these issues, it would be relevant to test silage plants with short vegetation period, which in the winter period will provide animals with high-quality succulent fodder.

Conflict of Interest: All authors declare no conflict of interest.

Materials and methods

In conditions of the Lejan and Pushkino villages of the Stepanavan province at the Lori region of Armenia, located at an altitude of 1100-1500 m above sea level, a combination of silage crops of sorghum, sunflowers and vetch was tested. In this zone, the climate is temperate, where typical alpine, cereal and legume plants are common among the wild vegetation cover. Summer here is moderately warm, relatively humid, rather temperate; in the first decade the climate is warm without precipitation. Frosts begin at the first half of October. The amount of annual atmospheric precipitation is 600-800 mm, most of which - about 400-600 mm - falls during the warm period.

The village of Lejan is located on the left side of Dzoraget at an altitude of 1460 m above sea level. Soil and climatic conditions of the area are unfavorable for the cultivation of field crops due to frequent hail. Population of the village is mainly engaged in the cultivation of cereal crops, potatoes and perennial grasses. In recent years, maize has also been cultivated, which is

used in animal husbandry for green fodder. However, this culture in the milk-wax phase is often exposed to frost. Animal husbandry is well developed here.

The village of Pushkino is located in the west of the Pushkino mountain range, at an altitude of 1520 m above sea level. The population here is also mainly engaged in the cultivation of potatoes and animal husbandry.

Experiments in the village of Lejan were carried out on a field plot and the predecessor was potato. In these two areas, the soil is leached chernozem.

Before setting up experiment, soil samples were taken for the identification of agro-chemical characteristics, in which the content of humus, general and mobile nutrients was determined.

Table 1

Agrochemical composition of the soils in Lejan and Pushkino

Locality	The humus content, %	Total nutrient content, %			Mobile soil nutrients, mg/100g			PH	The amount of absorbed bases, mg/eq. in 100g soil
		N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		
Lejan	4,9	0,33	0,34	1,70	17,6	6,95	39,1	6,1	42,6
Pushkino	5,7	0,35	0,29	1,90	18,9	7,70	40,6	6,6	44,7

According to the mechanical composition, the soil in Lejan is sand and clayey, and in Pushkino-clayey. The agrochemical composition of these soils is shown in Table 1.

The table data show that arable lands in Lejan and Pushkino are rich in organic matters (4.5-9.7%); the amount of humus and mobile nutrients is higher in Pushkino than in Lejan. In the soils of both localities, the content of mobile nitrogen is much higher (17.6 and 18.9 mg/100 g).

The content of total mobile phosphorus in the soil is lower, and that of exchangeable potassium is comparatively higher. It should be noted that if the weight of the arable layer at a depth of 25 cm of one hectare of leached chernozem is 3 million/kg, then according to calculations it turned out that in the arable layer of each hectare of Lejan leached chernozem there are 528 kg available nitrogen, 208 kg mobile nitrogen and 1173 kg exchangeable potassium [Bankrushenko L.V. 2014, Norov M.S. 2017, Miraliev D.R.2018]. In Pushkino, these figures were respectively: 567, 231 and 1218 kg/ha. According to the gradations compiled by the Scientific Center of Soil Science and Agrochemistry of Armenia, these chernozems are well supplied with mobile potassium.

In both localities, the pH of the aqueous solution has a slightly acidic reaction (6.1-6.6). The sum of absorbed bases is much higher (42.6-44.7 mg/ eq in soil).

Phosphorus and potash fertilizers with the dose of P₆₀K₆₀ were applied into the fall plowing of the experimental plot. In spring pre-sowing soil tillage was carried out, thereafter the seedling plot was laid out.

The experiments were set up in three replications, the size of registration plot was 30 m². Pure and mixed crops of sorghum, sunflowers and vetches were tested.

Experimental options are as follows:

1. Sorghum
2. Sunflower
3. Sorghum + vetch
4. Sunflower + vetch

The arrangement of options was carried out by the

randomization method.

Before sowing, the seeds were treated with Vitavax at a rate of 2.5 kg per ton of seeds. Sowing in Lejan and Pushkino was carried out in the third decade of May. Nitrogen fertilizers per appropriate dosages were applied, out of which N₃₀ was introduced along with the sowing, while N₆₀ was used in the form of top-dressing.

Sowing was carried out according to the pattern of 70x25x1. The sowing rate for sorghum is 20 kg/ha, and for sunflowers - 35 kg/ha. In case of combined sowing, the seeding rate in the variants was sorghum 10 + vetch 100 kg/ha and sunflower 15 + vetch 100 kg/ha. Sorghum variety Kormovaya -35, sunflowers - Aisa - 36 and vetch variety Narbonensis were selected for testing. Varieties are selected in a way so that the phases of their growth and development coincide and harvesting is carried out simultaneously. The harvest was subjected to mathematical processing using the dispersion method [Dospekhov B.A. 1973].

Research results

Studies have shown that at the end of vegetation period in conditions of Lejan village sunflower plants had a height of 150 cm, vetch 75 cm, and in Pushkino conditions 190 and 90 cm, respectively.

The growth and development of sorghum in the initial phase was relatively slow and lagged behind the growth and development of sunflowers. However, after formation of panicles, the plants began to quickly gain height, and in the milk-wax phase they were 100-115 cm tall.

The data of Table 2 show, that in the soil conditions of Pushkino village, the yield capacity is considerably higher than that of observed in Lejan village [Naumov M.K.1997]. So, in the variants of joint sowing, the yield of green mass was higher compared to individual sowings. In the sorghum + vetch variant, the yield surplus was 85.4 c/ha, and in the sunflower + vetch variant - 60 c/ha. Such yield increase was due to vetch plant.

Table 2

The effect of individual and combined sowings on the growth and yield capacity of the green mass

№	Options	Plant height, cm	Average yield, c/ha	Vetch yield surplus, c/ha	Green mass	
					Feed amount, unit	Amount of digestible nutrients, unit
Lejan						
1	Sorghum	115	312,7	-	7505	406,5
2	Sunflower	150	529,1	-	6349	529,1
3	Sorghum + vetch	117+75	366,5	53,8	7155	589,4
4	Sunflower + vetch	150+75	579,5	50,4	8366	702,5
Pushkino						
1	Sorghum	103	366,2	-	8789	476,1
2	Sunflower	190	681,1	-	8173	681,1
3	Sorghum + vetch	103+90	451,6	85,4	9133	766,5
4	Sunflower + vetch	190+90	741,1	60,0	10155	885,1

Among the variants of individual sowing the sunflower variant (529.1 and 681.1 c/ha) gave the best result both in Lejan and in Pushkino, compared to sorghum (312.7 and 366.2 c/ha).

In conditions of Lejan village, the number of feed units in the combination of sorghum + vetch, as compared to the sunflower + vetch variant, was higher by 1211, and

in Pushkino by 1022 feed units. At the same time, a different picture was observed in Lejan and Pushkino related to the yield of digestible proteins per hectare in co-sowing. In the sorghum+vetch variant, the yield of digestible proteins in both Lejan and Pushkinao villages is lower compared to the sunflower + vetch variant. In Lejan, the yield increase was 113.1 kg/ha, and in Pushkino - 118.6 kg/ha.

Table 3

The amount of green mass and its use

№	Options	Average yield, c/ha	Yield from 30m ² , kg	Harvest from three options, kg	Used, kg	
					For green fodder	For silage
Lejan						
1	Sorghum	312,7	94	280	180	100
2	Sunflower	529,1	159	470	270	200
3	Sorghum + vetch	366,5	110	300	200	100
4	Sunflower + vetch	579,5	175	500	300	200
Pushkino						
1	Sorghum	366,2	110	300	200	100
2	Sunflower	681,1	205	600	350	250
3	Sorghum + vetch	451,6	135	400	250	150
4	Sunflower + vetch	741,1	220	650	350	300

In conditions of Lejan village, 1550 kg of green mass were obtained in the result of three repetitions, out of which 950 kg were used for green fodder, and 600 kg - for silage.

In conditions of Pushkino, 1950 kg of green mass were obtained, out of which 1150 kg were used for green fodder and 800 kg - for silage (Table 3).

To assess the quality of the resulted green mass in average samples, the content of dry matter, crude/whole protein, protein, cellulose, as well as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium was determined.

Discussions

According to the research results, the qualitative data of the obtained yield showed that the dry matter

content is the same in both Lejan and Pushkino villages. However, it should be noted that in both localities, the best indicators were provided by the options of sunflower (16.2-16.6%) and sunflower + vetch (16.7%). The protein content in Pushkino was higher than in Lejan. The best result was provided by the sorghum + vetch variant (14.05%), and the cellulose content in both areas was higher in the combined variant of sunflower + vetch (6.2-6.4%).

The same pattern was observed in the content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. Regarding the plants it should be mentioned that in both areas the best results were provided by the pure sowings of sunflower and in the joint sowings of sunflower + vetch (Table 4).

Table 4

Some yield quality indicators (% in dry samples)								
№	Options	Dry matters	Whole protein	Proteins	Cellulose	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Lejan								
1	Sorghum	13,5	15,10	13,00	3,5	1,00	0,47	0,71
2	Sunflower	16,2	15,03	12,10	4,3	1,56	0,76	5,25
3	Sorghum + vetch	14,4	16,20	13,90	5,5	1,12	0,68	0,76
4	Sunflower + vetch	16,7	15,70	12,50	6,4	1,68	0,86	5,31
Pushkino								
1	Sorghum	13,7	15,50	13,30	3,7	1,05	0,51	0,76
2	Sunflower	16,6	15,11	12,70	4,8	1,59	0,75	5,30
3	Sorghum + vetch	14,8	16,50	14,05	5,2	1,16	0,85	0,85
4	Sunflower + vetch	16,7	15,90	13,00	6,2	1,72	0,89	5,43

Conclusion

1. In Lejan and Pushkino villages, a high yield of green mass was ensured by pure/individual sowing of sunflowers (529.1 and 681.1 c/ha) and joint sowing of sunflower + vetch (579.5 and 741.1 c/ha).

2. In both localities, the number of feed units and digestible proteins were higher in the sunflower + vetch variant (8366, 10155 and 702.5, 885.1) as well.

3. In conditions of Lejan and Pushkino villages, it is recommended to carry out joint sowing of sunflower and vetch, which provides a high yield of green mass and high-quality silage mass.

4. The recommended combination, as compared to the traditional maize cultivation in the region, eliminates the danger of winter frosts for almost a month. The combination of sunflower + vetch can be used both as silage and as green fodder.

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